

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

BOS MINUTES OF THE MEETING

The 5th meeting of BOS of College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas University was held at in Dean chamber of College of Physiotherapy, Pandeshwar on **06.03.2019**.

Members present were:

Dr. S. Rajasekar (Chairperson) *SR*

Dr. Ajay Kumar (Member) *Ajay*

Dr. Thrishala Noronha (Member) *Thrishala*

Dr. Annayya Kulal Ulthoor (Member) *Annayya*

Members not present were:

Dr. Padmakumar (External Member) **ABSENT**

Dr. Rakesh Krishna Kovela (External Member) **ABSENT**

Dr. Prameela P. Hubli (Member) **ABSENT**

At the onset the Chairperson, Dr. S. Rajasekar welcomed the members and placed the agenda for the deliberations of the members. The following deliberations were made as per the circulated agenda:

1. Confirmation of minutes of last meeting of the Board of Studies held on 02.11.2018.

- The minutes of the BOS meeting held on 2nd November 2018 were circulated among the BOS members. Since no comment has been received, this BOS has approved the minutes of the BOS meeting.

2. Revision of BPT 1st & 2nd semester Anatomy syllabus for 2019 batch of BPT.

- It was proposed by Dr. Annayya Kulal and seconded by Dr. Thrishala Noronha that some of the units from Anatomy-II subject of 2nd Semester has to be shifted to Anatomy-I subject of 1st Semester from BPT 2019 batch onwards in order to maintain equal distribution of topics.

-Resolution: All members discussed and resolved to recommend the revised syllabus for Anatomy-I and Anatomy-II of BPT 1st and 2nd semester (2019 batch) to the Academic Council for further approval.

3. Designing new MPT regulations and curriculum for the 2019 batch.

-It was proposed by the Chairperson and seconded by Dr. Padmakumar that the MPT curriculum for 2019 batch should be designed as per the choice based credit system and the regulations to be framed accordingly.

-Resolution: All members agreed and it was discussed and resolved that the Curriculum will be prepared by the month of May 2019 & will be recommended to the Academic Council for approval.

4. Introduction of new courses Basic Life Support (Theory) and Basic Life Support (Practical) in the 3rd semester BPT.

-Dr. Thrishala Noronha proposed to introduce new courses of BLS theory [SU19PT236(T)] and BLS practical [SU19PT236(VP)] during the 3rd semester as these courses will enhance the understanding and skills of students related to emergency treatment for patients.

-Resolution: The members discussed and finally considered and approved the syllabus to be recommended to the academic council for further approval. It was also agreed and approved that these changes will be applicable from 2019 batch onwards.

5. To consider change of a non-credit course "Yoga" running in 5th semester BPT to credit based course.

-It was suggested by Dr. Rajasekar S that, Yoga course which was earlier a non-credit course should be converted into a credit based course in the 5th semester BPT as it is one of the skill enhancement course and it can improve the credit requirements of the students. These modifications have been done considering the UGC recommendations.

-Resolution: The members considered the syllabus and finally, it was approved and recommended to the Academic Council for further approval. It was also agreed and approved that these changes will be applicable from 2019 batch onwards.

6. Planning the Academic calendar for odd semesters of BPT and MPT for the year 2019-20.

-Chairperson, Dr. S. Rajasekar requested that the academic calendar for the odd semesters of BPT and MPT be planned for the year 2019-20.

-Resolution: The members discussed and structured the academic calendar for the academic year 2019-20 of odd semesters of BPT and MPT.

7. Preparation of study material and question bank for the III semester BPT.

- Dr. S. Rajasekar proposed that the study material and question bank for the IV semester BPT (2018 batch) needs to be prepared.

-Resolution: All members discussed and resolved that the study material and question bank for the III semester BPT (2018 batch) be prepared by faculty members and submitted to the Dean by May 2019.

8. Formation of Board of examiners for BPT and MPT programmes.

The Chairperson explained the criteria related to the selection of BOE members and requested the Board to suggest names.

-Resolution: The Board prepared the list of BOE members in the Physiotherapy programmes for the academic year 2019-20 and resolved to recommend the same to the University.

9. Introduction of Value added courses for BPT and MPT for the year 2019-20.

Chairperson explained the requirement for adding value added course (not a part of curriculum) for BPT and MPT programmes.

-Resolution: The board discussed on this matter and it was decided that,

- for BPT 1st year- Basic Nursing and First Aid; BPT 2nd year- Diet and Nutrition; 3rd year- Yoga
- for MPT 1st year- Basic Life Support

The meeting ended with the Chairperson thanking all the members for being present giving their valuable suggestions.

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Chairperson
BOS, College of Physiotherapy

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

BOS MINUTES OF THE MEETING

The 6th meeting of BOS of College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas University was held at in Dean chamber of College of Physiotherapy, Pandeshwar on **04.10.2019**.

Members present were:

Dr. S. Rajasekar (Chairperson) *SR*

Dr. Ajay Kumar (Member) *Ajay*

Dr. Thrishala Noronha (Member) *Thrishala Noronha*

Dr. Annayya Kulal Ulthoor (Member) *Annayya*

Dr. Prameela P. Hubli (Member) *Prameela*

Members not present were:

Dr. Padmakumar (External Member) **ABSENT**

Dr. Rakesh Krishna Kovala (External Member) **ABSENT**

The Chairman welcomed all the members who were present for the meeting. The meeting thereafter deliberated on agenda items:

1. Confirmation of minutes of last meeting of the Board of Studies held on 6.3.2019

-As discussed, the syllabus of Anatomy-II course of 2nd semester BPT will be revised and implemented from the BPT batch of 2019. MPT curriculum will be structured as per the CBCS. The Academic calendar for odd semesters of BPT and MPT for the year 2019-20 was discussed and structured. The study material and question bank for 3rd semester BPT (2018 batch) will be prepared and submitted by May 2019.

-Rest approved.

2. Planning the Academic calendar for Even semesters of BPT and MPT for the year 2019-20.

-Chairperson, Dr. S. Rajasekar requested that the academic calendar for the even semesters of BPT and MPT be planned for the year 2019-20.

-Resolution: The members discussed and structured the academic calendar for the academic year 2019-20 of even semesters of BPT and MPT

3. Preparation of study material and question bank for the IV semester BPT.

- Dr. S. Rajasekar proposed that the study material and question bank for the IV semester BPT (2018 batch) needs to be prepared.

-Resolution: All members discussed and resolved that the study material and question bank for the IV semester BPT (2018 batch) be prepared by faculty members and submitted to the Dean by February 2020.

4. Preparation of Panel of examiners/gradation list.

-The Chairperson requested the Board members to prepare the panel of examiners for the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th and 6th semester end examination of BPT programme.

-Resolution: The Board members prepared the panel of examiners for the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th and 6th semester end examination of BPT and resolved to recommend the same to the University and send the panel of examiners list in a sealed cover to Registrar (Evaluation).

The meeting started at 10.30 am and ended at 12.30 pm with thanks to the Chair.

DRASEKAR

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Chairperson
BOS, College of Physiotherapy

[Signature]
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